

Deliverable No. 2.4

DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

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Deliverable 2.4

Report on changes in indicators of economic impact and in qualitative evaluation of potential social impact of the landing obligation over the course of the project (Month 42)

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Main Author: Katia Frangoudes (UBO, Beneficiary 7)

WP Leader: Ayoe Hoff, Peder Andersen
(IFRO-UoC, Beneficiary 6)

¹ PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Role	Name	Organisation	Date
Main Authors	Katia Frangoudes	UBO	18/02/2019
Task Leader	Katia Frangoudes	UBO	18/02/2019
WP leader	Ayoe Hoff , Peder Andersen	IFRO-UoC	18/02/2019
Coordinator	Clara Ulrich	DTU Aqua	18/02/2019

With report contributions from 5 co-authors from DiscardLess Project Participants

Name	Contribution to section(s)	Institution	DiscardLess beneficiary nr
Laurence Fauconnet	Interviews	IMAR-UAz	17
Kristian S. Plet-Hansen	Interviews and feel indicators	DTU Aqua	1
Toni Quetglas	Minutes of meetings	IEO--UoC	3
Gabrielle Heyvaert	Organisation of workshops	Pole Aquimer	16
George Triantaphyllidis	Interviews, Minutes of meetings, Greek National Survey	NAYS	15

Executive Summary of D2.4.

Report on changes in indicators of economic impact and in qualitative evaluation of potential social impact of the landing obligation over the course of the project

Box 1: Report Highlights and key results

LO implementation was negatively criticised by fishers

Fishers perceive LO as top down decision responding to the interest of other economic sectors or lobby forces

Fishers consider that LO will impact negatively their activity

Change of negative opinion need communication about LO using the right arguments

Fisheries managers (PO's) who understood why LO should be implemented used the right arguments to convince fishers to register discarded in logbook.

Box 2: Methods used

Interviews, Organisation of focus groups, Analysis of qualitative data, Quantitative survey (postal in France and face to face in Greece) and analysis.

Box 3: How these results can be used and by who?

The results can be used by policy makers at regional, national and EU level. But also by fisheries managers and fishers' representatives as well scientists interesting about this issue.

The results of this task were used for the publication of two chapters in the DiscardLess book and one Article. The results of the survey can be used for publication of Articles in specialized relevant Journals.

Box 4: Policy implications

Clarification of some aspects of the Article 15 of Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 is recommended because it can help the implementation of the LO.

1 Introduction and methodology

The objective of DiscardLess task 2.5 (reported in this Deliverable D2.4) was to follow the evolution of fishers' and other stakeholders' opinion regarding the Landing Obligation (LO) and its implementation process in different Cases Studies. To this end, it was decided to trace, in a few case study areas, the same indicators over time in order to identify changes and evolutions. Stakeholders' opinions, gathered annually within the framework of this task, provided also information for the implementation of other tasks (Cf Deliverables D4.1, D4.4, D7.3, D7.4, D8.7). The case studies selected were in North Aegean Sea, Boulogne-Sur-Mer, Azores islands and in the Western Mediterranean (Spain/Balearic Islands and France/Gulf of Lyon). Reports of these tasks and deliverables have been submitted and some of them are already available on the project website. This document contains the main information collected since the beginning of the project and focuses on the results of the national surveys conducted in France beginning of 2018. Similarities, analogies, differences are brought out to illustrate opinion trends.

This task has been fully implemented in the following Member States : France, Greece and Portugal. In France, investigations were conducted over several case study areas: The North Sea, the English Channel (for Eastern part only and later extended to the Western part also), the Celtic Sea and the Bay of Biscay. The analyses in Greece were performed in the North Aegean-Gulf of Thermaikos and in Portugal, in the Azores Archipelagos. In these three Member States, semi-structured interviews with fishers, auctions representatives, managers in Administration, scientists and NGOs were conducted. Later in the project, DiscardLess organised also workshops where the main results of each Work Package were presented and discussed, with the participants representing almost the same groups of actors previously interviewed in this task 2.5 (cf Deliverable D8.7). In the last year of the project, a national survey was conducted in France and Greece by UBO, the leader of this task. The survey had the combined objectives of first enlarging the number of interviewees and second obtaining a better vision of changing attitudes of fishers towards the LO. In France, 450 questionnaires were sent by post to fishers' homes, and three months were given to respond. 150 anonymous responses were received and analysed. In Greece, the questionnaire was conducted face to face mainly in the North Aegean Sea. 70 fishers responded, and the results of the survey is also presented here.

Western Mediterranean (Spain/Balearic Islands and France/Gulf of Lyon) and Denmark were the two other case studies involved in this task. Different methodologies were used in these countries. In the Western Mediterranean cases, DiscardLess partners organised annual focus groups or workshops. The first one brought together French and Spanish stakeholders and the next two meetings were organised in Balearic Islands. All these meetings brought together fishers' representatives, POs, net-makers, auctions representatives, administration and Environmental NGOs. In Denmark, interviews on the landing obligation were performed in 2015-2016, more specifically dedicated to Electronic monitoring (Plet-Hansen et al., 2017)². Secondly a list of indicators was prepared during the first year of the project

² Schreiber Plet-Hansen, K., Qvist Eliassen, S., Mortensen, L. O., Bergsson, H., Olesen, H. J., & Ulrich, C. (2017). Remote electronic monitoring and the landing obligation – some insights into fishers' and fishery inspectors' opinions. *Marine Policy*, 76, 98-106. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpol.2016.11.028

and filled in 2016 and 2017 by the representatives of the fishing industry (POs), with the supervision of the national partner.

Table 1. DiscardLess case Studies and methodology for Task 2.5.

Cases studies	Methodology
English Channel and North Sea (France)	Interviews, Focus Groups, National postal survey, National DiscardLess Workshop
Celtic Sea (France)	Interviews, Focus Groups, National postal survey, National DiscardLess Workshop
Bay of Biscay (France)	Interviews, Focus groups, National postal survey, National DiscardLess Workshop
French Mediterranean Sea (West Mediterranean)	Transnational focus group (1), local focus group, national postal Survey, National DiscardLess workshop
Azores Archipelagos	Focus group with fishers (1), Interviews with fishers, actions and fisheries administration from three Islands, 1 working group with representatives of fishers and regional fisheries administration
Balearic Islands (West Mediterranean)	1 transnational focus group, 2 regional focus groups (Cataluna and Balears islands), interviews with NGOs and national fisheries administration, fishers.
East Mediterranean (Greece)	Interviews, National face to face surveys, 2 DiscardLess Workshops (Athens and Nea Michaniona)
North Sea (Denmark)	List of Indicators (filled by POs) and interviews

The main themes covered by interviews, focus groups and survey were the following:

1. Knowledge of fishers and fisheries managers on Article 15 of the CFP and their general opinion about the LO
2. Stakeholders' opinion about the LO implementation process
3. LO impacts on work on-board fishing vessels, economic situation of fishing enterprises
4. Reasons for discarding (technical, biological, economic, regulations, etc.)
5. Current practices to avoid unwanted catches and future adaptation strategies
6. Fishers' needs from science and acceptability of observers on board fishing vessels
7. Which use for unwanted and unavoidable catches

2 Presentation and analysis of the qualitative and quantitative data.

Changes and evolution of economic impacts of the LO on fishing vessels is not addressed in this deliverable as the implementation of the LO has been slow and the vessels have not landed discards so far, so no changes have actually been observed. The economic statistics available at European level is the second reason preventing us to show this impact, as the latest year of data available is 2016 (Annual Economic Report, STECF 2018)³, which doesn't allow to follow changes and evolutions since the implementation of the LO.

2.1 Knowledge about Article 15 and its implementation process

During the first and second year of the DiscardLess project (2015, 2016), interviewed vessel owners and crews had limited knowledge about Article 15 of the Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 and even lesser information on its implementation process. This lack of knowledge was observed in France, Greece, the Balearic and Azores Islands and, to a lesser degree, in Denmark. Two basic elements in this study was to understand the reasons for this lack of knowledge as well gather the general opinion of fishers towards the LO and Article 15. Since fishers, as the main group impacted by this new policy, are not convinced about the LO, its implementation can be compromised. According to the Regulation 1380/2013, the LO should be gradually implemented and fully implemented from 2019 in all Member States. Grasping the general perception of European fishers can help to identify the difficulties and perspectives of the LO's acceptability and legitimacy.

2.1.1 Fishers' knowledge and perception about the LO

The majority of individual artisanal fishers and crew members interviewed within the framework of the DiscardLess project admitted to have very little or no knowledge at all about the LO and its implementation process. At the same time, it was observed that fishers' representatives of the different regions or countries (Denmark, Azores, France, Balearic Islands) had better knowledge about the LO and the implementation process thanks to their participation at national or transnational (Advisory Councils) meetings discussing the LOs' issues. It can be said that fishers sitting in organisations and other bodies know globally the provisions of the LO, but still do not understand the details and the main challenges of its implementation. Managers of POs or fishers' organisations are better informed about the difficulties that national fishing fleets will face during the implementation phase. Interviews showed also that national and regional administrations in the Member States have good knowledge of the LO. The following table is presenting few quotations from interviews realised in the different case studies.

Table 2: Knowledge of LO quotations from the interviews realised between 2015-2017

³

https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reports/economic/-/asset_publisher/d71e/document/id/2262395?inheritRedirect=false&redirect=https%3A%2F%2Fstecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu%3A443%2Freports%2Feconomic%3Fp_p_id%3D101_INSTANCE_d71e%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-2%26p_p_col_pos%3D1%26p_p_col_count%3D2

<i>"I never heard about LO". (fisher from Azores).</i>
<i>"Do TAC managed species should be included in the LO?" (fisher Azores member of Advisory Council)</i>
<i>"I heard about the LO two years ago but its implementation calendar is obscure for me». (fishers operating in Celtic Sea, France)</i>
<i>"I don't know anything about the LO. EU policies are common for all MS but people from Northern Europe don't understand how we are working in the Mediterranean as we cannot understand how they work! All of us to follow the same rules this is not possible. The LO is not for our waters". (trawler fisher from Greece)</i>
<i>"Our fishers were informed about the LO during the consultation process of the new reform". (Fisheries authorities, Greece)</i>
<i>"I know the LO because I am elected at the regional fisheries committee". (Fisher operating in Bay of Biscay, France)</i>

In interviews realised between 2015 and 2017, Greek fishers said that they *"never heard about the LO because nobody informed them"* and complained that they didn't have *"the opportunity to express their opinion"* about it. The national fisheries authorities consider that Greek fishers were informed about this rule during the consultation process of the CFP. Azoreans and West Mediterranean individual fishers declared that they were not informed, while fishers' representatives sitting in Advisory Councils said that they know the LO, but not in detail. It seems that the information didn't really reach fishers and crew members directly concerned by this obligation.

French individual fishers considered also that they weren't informed about Article 15 and its implementation, despite the fact that during the consultation process on the green paper of the CFP they took part in regional meetings and expressed a negative vision concerning the "zero discard" rule (name given to the LO by French fishers) (<https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/reform/consultation/received>). Since the adoption of the new CFP regulations in 2013, French national fisheries authorities and representatives of POs and Fisheries committees have all been members of the national group MOOD (Groupe d'Echange sur la Mise en Oeuvre de l'Obligation de Débarquement) that discusses the issues related to the LO implementation. This working group played an important role in the formulation of the exemptions requested by French fisheries authorities in different regional seas. Following the exemptions granted, the French national fisheries authorities prepared information sheets on the LO to acquaint all individual fishers with the LO implementation process and the nature of these exemptions. These sheets were circulated to all Regional Fisheries Committees and POs. Despite this effort, French individual fishers keep saying in 2017 that they are not informed about the LO and its implementation process in practice.

The lack of information and knowledge about the LO as reported by French fishers can be explained by the following quote *"EU didn't find the right words and arguments to explain such unjust decision"* (PO manager). If managers working for POs and fisheries organisations consider the LO as an unjust decision, then it is almost impossible to inform fishers about it. For the same group of managers, the

wording of Article 15 is not advantageous to fishers because it almost accuses them of being the “destructors” of the resources. And the European legislators “punished” them for their bad action with Article 15. So the LO is perceived by all as a punishment. Within this cognitive and behavioural context, it appears difficult to disseminate the provisions of Article 15. Another criticism brought out by the interviews adds further to this. It relates to the method used by the European institutions: *“First they voted and then asked MS to apply and inform fishers”*. As a consequence, national fisheries administrations don’t have the right arguments to justify unpopular decisions and *“fishers cannot understand the reasons and reject the LO (...). They don’t even want to discuss about it. Now it is too late to change this negative perception for EU and for the LO”* (fisheries manager).

The only fora where the fisheries industry discusses the LO and its implementation and impacts are the Advisory Councils (ACs) at regional seas level. But these Councils are shared with Environmental NGOs; so there is no possibility to express fully one’s ideas. Debates and negotiations within ACs were concentrated on exemptions, improvement of discard data, impacts of the LO and adaptation strategies. In one case (Mediterranean Advisory Council-MEDAC), a Joint Recommendation was elaborated⁴. People participating in ACs meetings are usually managers or fishers’ representatives. The first group understands and discusses easily the technical parts of LO, as for example the issues of choke species and exemptions. The second group with elected representatives of fishers (Chair of fishers’ organisations and POs) is reluctant to discuss LO as soon as it leaves the meeting room because *“during the meetings nobody is hearing the fishers voice”* (AC North western waters, North Sea), or *“members of ACs during meetings are thinking only about their own fishers and interests; so negotiations do not seek to examine the global interests of the industry”* (Bretagne representatives). This criticism underlines the difficulties of fishers’ representatives from different Member States when it comes to sharing the same vision and claims and having a common voice. And ENV-NGOs are not that ready to trust fishers and listen to their problems. The second quote reveals another difficulty faced by fishers within ACs: *“ENV-NGOs don’t want to value the initiatives taken by us (fishers) because they don’t trust the results”* (Regional fisheries Committee of Haut de France, National Fisheries Committee, Paris). All projects run by fishers’ organisations in France, as CarRejets, EODE, were conducted in collaboration with scientists. When ENV-NGOs contest their results as not being scientific in nature (e.g. results of CarRejets at North Sea AC), they are not in line with the dispositions of the EU regulations 1380/2013 and 508/2014 asking for increased collaboration between scientists and the industry. So fishers cannot understand such attitude; and they usually avoid bringing home what happens in the AC meetings.

The following figure presents the results of the two national surveys concerning fisher’s knowledge on the LO, in France and in Greece (realised between December 2017 and beginning of 2018).

⁴ See MEDAC 2014 http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_pareri_lettere/2014/09/159_medac_draft_joint_rec_management_plan_discards_small_pel.pdf, Ref.: 190/2016 of June 8, 2016: http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_pareri_lettere/2016/06/190_medac_jr_lo_demersal_8june.pdf and 2018: http://en.med-ac.eu/files/documentazione_pareri_lettere/2018/05/132_medac_jr_lo_species_annexiii_regmed_en.pdf

Table 3. Vessel owners' knowledge about the LO, France and Greece

	France	Greece
Don't know at all	6 (4.28%)	24 (34.28%)
Have little knowledge	68 (48.57%)	45 (64.28%)
I know well	40 (28.57%)	1 (1.43%)
I am without opinion	26 (18.57%)	0
TOTAL	140	70

Source: National Surveys 2018, DiscardLess

Table 3 above shows first, a great number of fishers declare having little knowledge about the LO; second, French fishers have better knowledge than Greek fishers. Only one Greek fisher knows well the LO, compared to 40 French in 2018.

The responses to the survey, demonstrate that French fishers' knowledge about the LO evolved since 2015 when the first semi-structured interviews were conducted. One observes also that Greek fishers' knowledge and opinion about the LO didn't evolve. This gap between the two countries is probably due to the quasi absence of State-recognized fishers' organisations, including POs, in Greece. Relations between national fisheries authorities and the national federation of large fleets are rare. The National federation of large-scale fleets (PEPMA) doesn't have the financial capacity to pay for member fees at MEDAC, and they did not take part in these meetings for many years. The same observation is true for Small-Scale Fleet (SSF) organisations. Within this context, it is easy to understand why Greek fishers have never heard about the LO, and the DiscardLess questionnaire was almost the first initiative to talk about the LO to these fishers. The Greek fisheries authorities cannot substitute for the fishers' organisations role in these matters. In countries like France, where POs and Fisheries elected organisations are present and active, information reached individual fishers. In Denmark, fishers, are also well organised in POs and have good knowledge about the LO. Nevertheless, they also see Article 15 as a bad decision.

2.1.2 Summary

Individual fishers and crew interviewed or participating in focus groups had little or no knowledge about the LO and its implementation process. Fishers' representatives from the different countries and regions (Denmark, Azores, France, Balearic Islands) participating in national or transnational meetings (ACs) have better knowledge of the LO and its implementation process. Fishers sitting in organisations or other bodies know the general provisions of the LO but not the details, and are unable to anticipate the potential problems raised by this rule. Only the managers of POs and fishers' elected organisations have the capacity to anticipate future problems. The difference in knowledge demonstrates that the fisheries industry is not a homogenous group. So, the LO implementation at national level can only be achieved if the different groups of knowledge communicate between themselves, which is not the case until now. Knowledge is maintained by fisheries managers representing individual fishers, except in

Denmark. The situation starts little by little to change in countries or harbours where fisheries managers have been strongly sensitized to LO (eg. Boulogne Sur Mer, France).

2.2 Fishers opinion about the LO

Interviewed fishers in the different case studies expressed a bad opinion concerning the LO. For Mediterranean fishers, the LO is tailored for Atlantic fisheries because it *“doesn't take into account the particularities of Mediterranean fisheries”* (Greek, French, Balearic Islands). Mediterranean fishers criticized the EU because it considers all regional seas as similar *“(..). EU asks us to apply the LO? It is not fair (..), our activity is not the same as in the North Sea”* (Greek trawler). Other fishers considering the CFP and its common rules as unfair are the Small-Scale (SSF) ones, because *“EU doesn't see them”* and *“ignores their needs”* (French fisher).

Fishers operating in the Atlantic see the LO as *“a rule without rule”* (Azores fisher). Because species under quota system should be landed and accounted for in the quota, *“just to be thrown away as trash”* because Article 15 doesn't authorize its use for human consumption. In the Azores as in other areas of EU (France, Greece), discards are given to crew members either *“to sustain family livelihoods or to sustain family income”* (crew members in Sao Miguel Azores, N. Michaniona, Greece). Implementation of the LO will put an end to this traditional social practice.

For fishers, *“with good knowledge of the CFP”,* the LO means *“more restrictions in fisheries, particularly for trawlers”* (trawl fisher, France). French trawler owners of the Bay of Biscay, the English Channel, the Celtic Sea, the Gulf of Lion, and also Greeks, believe that Article 15 target *“is to ban trawling”*. For them, this negative opinion about trawlers is based on the general belief that considers this gear as *“scrapers of the bottom”* or *“destructors of resources”* (Greece, France). Some didn't hesitate to speak about an *“eradication of trawling”* (France, Greece). These restrictive rules are based on an unjust representation of the efforts made by this profession in matters of *“resources management”,* thus making this activity *“financially profitable”*. Its destruction will mean jobs losses. All interviewed fishers considered that they made progress in resources management, as compared to the past. But the EU and others don't recognize these efforts, and Article 15 is proof of it (France, Azores, Greece). To reverse this negative perception, trawl fishers mentioned the positive impacts of their activity on the ecosystem. *“In areas where trawling is forbidden, when we return back we cannot find fish”* (France, Greece). For them, banning trawling in some areas impacts negatively the resources. This general belief dominates fishers thinking in many countries. The following table presents quotations originated from different Member States expressing fishers' opinion towards LO. They were chosen because they were expressed by fishermen from all the countries involved in this task.

Table 4: Opinion on LO: quotations from the interviews realised between 2015-2017.

<p><i>“We are against the regulation; now we have to find the means and arguments to fight against the rules”.</i> (managers French PO)</p>

<i>"Such a rule is not applicable as it is" (Azores, fishers)</i>
<i>"Is LO targeting the production of fish meal for aquaculture? A sector competing our products". (Greek Fishers)</i>
<i>"Politicians satisfied the claims of Environmental NGO's and the aquaculture sector". (French fishers).</i>
<i>"I hope that processing industry should not encourage fishermen to continue land discards». (scientist, France)</i>
<i>«Why Environmental NGO's ask us to land small fish having high rate of survival (eg. Sole, plaice, Norway nephrops, etc...). Are they concerned with conservation of resources»! (French trawler fisher)</i>
<i>Nobody take care of fishers! We done so much to improve fisheries management and nobody takes care". (French fisher)</i>
<i>"Note that these measures go against what we had done so far: fish shipments under the legal landing size have been confiscated up to now, and we now have to let them land them. (Catalan fisheries administration)".</i>

"Fishers feel to be governed by an immaterial octopus" (Fisheries managers, France). This quote summarizes how fishers view EU decisions. A Greek fisher, as soon as he understood what the LO means, asked the following question: *"They are crazy in Europe? They don't have something more useful to do"*? And he added: *"Will they also ask Bluefin tunas and dolphins to land all the fish they eat"*. These two quotes show how top-down decisions are perceived and how difficult it is to implement them. Decisions taken without consultation of the direct users (fishers) are not easy to be enforced. Politicians, DG MARE, national fisheries administrations staff and fisheries managers working for the industry and scientists speak and understand the same language. But this is not the case for artisanal fishers who are far away from decision-making tables and lack access to information. Good communication on new fisheries rules is needed, especially when rules are unpopular, due to their restrictive character. Their enforcement is not an easy task. Right and rational arguments could convince fishers if they are well presented. For the moment, they have the feeling that decision-makers don't trust them.

The following Tables 5 and 6 present the opinion of French and Greek fishers on the LO. In both countries larger vessels have more negative opinion than small-scale fishers in both countries.

Table 5. Opinion of French fishers about the LO by size of vessels in 2018

	Vessels >12m of length)	Vessels <12 m length
Very bad opinion	76 (70.37%)	12 (41.38%)
Bad opinion	18 (16.67%)	4 (13.79%)

	Vessels >12m of length)	Vessels <12 m length
Good	4 (3.70%)	2 (6.89%)
Very good	9 (8.33%)	7 (24.14%)
Without opinion	1 (0.92%)	4 (13.79%)
TOTAL	108	29

Source: National Surveys 2018, DiscardLess

Table 6. Opinion of Greek fishers about LO by size of vessels in 2018

	Vessels >12m of length	Vessels <12 m length
Very bad opinion	48 (77.42%)	1 (16.67%)
Bad opinion	6 (9.68%)	1 (16.67%)
Very good	2 (3.22%)	3 (50.00%)
Without opinion	6 (9.68%)	1 (16.67%)
TOTAL	62	6

Source: National Survey, 2018, DiscardLess.

The responses of French (table 5) and Greek (table 6) fishers to the national survey are similar to the qualitative data obtained during the interviews. The bad opinion on LO continues and makes its implementation difficult.

2.2.1 The implementation process of LO

“Only three years were given to implement LO. This period is indeed very short to change significantly fishers' behaviour, mentalities and fishing practices. For the EU, it is possible; but for us, it is not realistic” (French Fisheries manager).

“LO cannot be applied to our fisheries” is the opinion of Greek trawler owners, as well as other Mediterranean fishers (Trawl association of Nea Michaniona). Finally, did the joint recommendation produced by MEDAC, with the support and agreement of fisheries authorities of all Member States, demonstrated this difficulty? Is this difficulty related to the ecosystem of the Mediterranean Sea, as fishers want to tell? Is it revealing the incapacity of national authorities to apply this unpopular rule? Is it showing the complexity of using all technical measures to implement the LO. In this regional sea, only

few fishers were informed about the LO, and even about the exemptions that were granted. All admitted that they do not apply the LO. They don't register discards in logbooks and don't register the number of slipping operations practised with the purse seine. Until the date of the interviews and survey, no significant changes were produced at local levels. The following table is presenting quotations related to fishers' opinion on LO coming from the interviews. The chosen quotations point out the different problems and perspectives related to LO implementation.

Table 7: LO implementation: quotations from the interviews realised between 2015-2017

<i>"We (fisheries sector) are not sure how to carry out the implementation of the regulation. Reducing discards to zero is unfeasible". (Balearic Islands fishers)</i>
<i>"How we can implement the LO on a small vessel like this? in a space of 3,2m we are three persons so we cannot move (...) if we could use a single tank it might be possible to do it but it seems that we have to separate discards species by species". (French, small trawler)</i>
<i>"Impossible to implement the regulation because there is no ancillary industry to process discards". (Balearic Islands fishers)</i>
<i>"Landing discards means that they will be counted in our quotas". (Azores fisher)</i>
<i>"As long as there is no pressure from public authorities, we do not care". (French trawler)</i>
<i>"We need to register our discards and be able justify granted exemptions". (French fisher)</i>
<i>"Need to declare discards in a case of uplift quotas". (French fisher)</i>
<i>"I tell my son to learn how to declare discards on logbook because I feel that we will have more control at sea". (French fisher)</i>
<i>"On our vessels we are now testing the registration on logbook". (French fisher)</i>
<i>"In a case that our vessels are equipped with a camera others countries should also do it". (Danish fisher).</i>
<i>"Our vessels begin to register discards. Some of them are registering everything, others little by little". (PO managers, Bretagne Nord, France)</i>

The above quotations can be perceived as contradictory but they illustrate well the current debate about the LO implementation. Fishers' opinion seems to change as some of them understand that registered quotas can be useful to justify granted exemptions and also be beneficial for them. Old fishers think that

young generation will deal better than them with the new tools on board. This modification is also illustrated in Tables 8 and 9 presenting the results of national surveys. It appears that French fishers have a better knowledge about the enforcement process compared to Greek fishers. But Greek fishers participating to the national survey seem to have better knowledge than in the first period of the DiscardLess project.

Table 8. Number and percent of French and Greek fishers knowing that the LO is implemented in 2018.

	France	Greece
YES	83 (59.71%)	59 (84.29%)
NO	56 (40.29%)	11 (15.71%)
TOTAL	139	70

Source: National Surveys 2018, DiscardLess

Table 9. Number and percent of fishers having heard about exemptions in France and Greece in 2018

	France	Greece
YES	95 (69.34%)	59 (84.29%)
NO	42 (30.66%)	11 (15.71%)
TOTAL	137	70

Source: National Surveys 2018, DiscardLess

The results of the national surveys depicted in Tables 8 and 9 show that fishers' knowledge about the LO has evolved with the time. In France, this change is probably linked to the different initiatives conducted by fishers' organisations to test the LO implementation or more selective gears. For example, the Regional Fisheries Committee of Haut de France, tested the full implementation of the LO at sea and land (EODE project, 2014-2016, <https://www.comitedespeches-hautsdefrance.fr/nos-actions/gestion-de-ressource/eode/>). A fishing vessel targeting sole registered its discards in the logbook and then landed it to test the functioning of this system. Small soles were stocked at the quay in front of Boulogne-Sur-Mer auction market; but local processing industry and auction didn't collect them. After two days, the fish was thrown in the trash bin by fishers. This experience showed that land infrastructures are not ready to cope with the LO. But it provides to fisheries committees the right arguments to justify fishers' hesitation and non-compliance behaviour regarding the LO. If nobody is ready to apply the LO, why should fishers start doing it first?

Boulogne-Sur-Mer fishers, as elsewhere in France, don't register and don't land discards, and that despite the demand formulated by their POs asking to register and then return them back to the sea. For POs, data on discards are necessary to justify granting exemptions, particularly those of *de minimis*. This exemption is responding partially to the choke species issue, at least for the most problematic species. According to one PO manager, *"France should continue to benefit from the de minimis exemption to avoid that our fleet stays for many days in port"* (PO in Bretagne). Gathering discard data will help understand what are the real difficulties faced by the French fleets. *Without data, it is difficult to convince decision-makers about the impossibility to implement and apply the LO*. The last argument used to convince skippers and fishers to register discards is the establishment of *"historical rights"* which may help in the future *to negotiate additional quotas* (POs managers). French large fishing companies produced an explicative note addressed to skippers to explain the reasons for registering discards. According to the manager of one of those companies, skippers don't want to spend time registering discards; and they always respond that the fishing area where they operate *"doesn't have discards"*. During the interview, a skipper of the same company said *"he will never start registering discards until he gets a fine"*. According to a Boulogne-sur-Mer PO, only one of its members was logging discards in 2018. During a control on board, he listened to what controllers told him about the obligation to register discards. Failure to comply is sanctioned by a penalty. Since then, he has been registering discards, but without landing them. So are controls and fines the best tool to enforce the implementation of the LO?

Another difficulty found among French artisanal fishers is the understanding of the principles and the functioning of exemptions. This difficulty is higher among fishers operating in different regional seas or those practising different gears during the year. For example, fishers of Boulogne-Sur-Mer or Finistère (the first working simultaneously in East Channel and North Sea, and the second in the Celtic Sea and the Bay of Biscay) cannot understand why exemptions are different between the two areas or between two gears. For example, in East Channel netters have an exemption of 3% of sole but not trawlers. *"Rules implemented by the French authorities are difficult to comprehend by fishers"*. (PO manager).

In Azores also, fishers said that the LO is not yet implemented. For this small-scale fleet, discards are not a big issue: it is using selective gears and has limited discards. Greek fishers having continuously problems to use the logbook, refuse to add a new burden: discards remain unregistered. In fact, nobody asked them officially to register them, unlike the French POs. So why should they do it?

Figure 1 shows that registration of discards is not yet applied by the French fleet. POs should find better arguments to convince fishers and skippers about the utility of such data. Fishers consider that registering discards is *"a waste of time"*; or that it is *"better not to start because, as soon as they do it, they don't have the possibility to back out"*. Without enforcement, it is difficult to move forward with the process.

Figure 1. Number of fishers declaring and registering discards in France in 2018

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

Figure 1 shows that registration of discards is not yet applied by the majority of the French fleet but twenty percent of them is doing it. POs and fisheries committees should find better arguments to convince fishers and skippers about the utility of such data.

2.3 Expected impact of the implementation of the LO

The negative impacts of the LO to the fishing industry, fishing enterprises and ecosystem were mentioned by all interviewed fishers in France (English East Channel, Celtic Sea, and Bay of Biscay, North Sea, Gulf of Lion), Denmark (North Sea), West Mediterranean (Balearic Islands, France) and North Aegean Sea (Greece) and Azores in the first years of the DiscardLess project. All of them said that the LO will impact trawlers and other gears. Figures 2 and 3 present the results of a survey conducted in France and Greece by gear. These results confirm these opinions, at least for trawlers. Métiers using more selective gears attract less negative opinions.

Figure 2. Expected impact of the LO on fishing by type of gear, France 2018

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

Figure 3. Expected impact of the LO on fishing by fishing gear, Greece 2018

Source: National survey in Greece, 2018, DiscardLess

For all interviewed fishers, working conditions on-board will be worsened due to the increased working time to sort fish (Danish, French, Spanish Med fishers). Another argument used by fishers was that the additional work will probably require the employment of one more crew member. As a consequence, crew members' income will decrease in MS where they are paid on the basis of share. Vessel owners fear that crew will never accept to work more for a lesser income. Additional working hours can increase also the risks of accident at sea. Handling "unwanted catches" is perceived by crew unions as a deterioration of social rights. For all these reasons vessels' owners are convinced that crew members will react negatively to the LO implantation. In some Member States, working conditions and rights of

crew members are regulated by a collective agreement negotiated between union of crew members and vessel owners. In the case of the LO implementation, these agreements should be renegotiated to include more working hours and the rules of share calculation (e.g. in France).

Safety of vessels is also mentioned in relation to the transportation of “unwanted catches”, as the boats will be heavier (eg. France, Balearic Islands, Azores).

The second important impact mentioned is profitability of the fishing enterprises (English Channel, Celtic Sea, North Sea, North Aegean, Azores). Figures 3 and 4 displays expected economic impacts in France and Greece in 2018. Fishers operating in the mentioned regional seas believe that the LO will increase the operational cost of the boats (fuel, ice, additional work, auction taxes). New investments to cope with the LO should be done, as for example selective gears, increase the storage capacity of the boats. All these additional costs cannot be covered by fishers and require the support of EMFF. In some MS, this fund has taken more time than expected to be implemented (eg. France, Greece), and only a few fishers could benefit from financial support.

Figure 4. Expected Economic impact of the LO implementation by gear and vessels, France 2018

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

Figure 5. Expected Economic impact of the LO implementation by fishing gear, number of vessels, Greece 2018

Source: National survey in Greece 2018, DiscardLess

Small-scale fishers think that fuel consumption will increase due to lack of storage capacity on their vessels. They should return more often to port (East English Channel fishers, Greek fishers). The storage space on deck is limited and cannot contain “*unwanted catches*” because “*sanitary norms don't allow them to mix fish for human consumption and discards in the same place*”.

In larger vessels, the limited size of storage is also a real issue because “*vessels will be rapidly crowded with species without economic value, and profitability will be lower*” (French fisheries managers). A reduction of the fishing fleet due to lack of profitability was also mentioned as another potential impact of the LO. Lack or reduction of profitability can require a redistribution of national quotas; and reducing the number of vessels would be the only solution. But this represents high social risks as the prospect of harbours without vessels may be viewed as unacceptable in European societies

For French fisheries managers, the profitability of the fleet is the most important impact of the LO, and the two following quotes are an appropriate expression of the problem. “*If vessels are full with species without commercial value, then it will be difficult to be profitable, especially in the case of species that cannot be sold (no quota, undersized fish)*”, and “*if vessels, due to choke species, stay in the harbour for six months*”. They hope that French authorities and society will react against “*the destruction of French fisheries, which is not socially acceptable*” (PO employee).

2.4 Most mentioned causes for discarding

The main reasons for discarding are related to:

- 1) the EU regulatory framework: no quotas, or quotas that don't match with catches, the rules of proportionality in catches compositions (EC n° 494/2002), minimum legal size (North Sea, Celtic

- Sea, East and West English Channel, Bay of Biscay, Greece, Balearic Islands, Azores), forbidden species with 0 TAC (Undulate rays, Deep Water Sharks...).
- 2) Economic reasons are also mentioned, especially high grading, practiced by PO decisions targeting market regulations. In France, high grading is practised for species without commercial value (e.g plaice, whiting...) and with market value (cod, Norway lobsters, etc). Fishers spoke also of seasonal bottlenecks on market for some species and of market regulation through fish supply rules.
 - 3) The last reasons are technical and biological reasons, as for example fishing areas with high presence of juveniles (Danish, Greek, French fishers), as well as poor conservation of species (e.g. hake). By-catches also were mentioned, and good handling of some species and damaged fish were the others.

Figures 6 and 7 present the main reasons for discards in Greece and France, as given by fishers in the national surveys.

Figure 6. Reasons for discarding in Greece (scoring)

Source: National survey in Greece 2018, DiscardLess

Figure 7. Reasons for discards, France (scoring)

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

2.5 Current strategies to avoid discards and possible strategies for adaptation

The most mentioned “adaptation strategies” in the interviews are the flexibilities given by Article 15, the exemptions of *de minimis*, fish survival and disproportionate cost. Exemptions are perceived by many stakeholders as an implementation of the LO. For example, Mediterranean fishers are exempted from the LO (main commercial species). But many of them don’t know what is Article 15 and what are its dispositions and why they are exempted. Small-scale fishers (SSF) from all areas don’t know either what the LO is, though during national surveys and interviews all said that this rule will impact them less than trawlers. This perception is representing SSF vessels using selective gears, which are claiming a collective exemption with the argument that “we discard less”. Small-scale vessels using towed gears (it is the case in France) are satisfied with the national exemptions because in their zones of operation there are more nurseries and juveniles.

In France, larger vessels are partly satisfied with the exemption of *de minimis*. The survival exemption satisfy them more, as a lot of them think that many species can survive if they are returned immediately in the sea, and that “they should not be landed”. One of them is the Norway lobster in the Bay of Biscay. The exemption granted for this species improved the working conditions of crew members on board, now equipped with a table that makes it easier to sort out undersized Norway lobsters and return them back into the sea. Without the LO, crew members would have continued to sort out this species kneeling on the deck as they have been doing in the past.

2.5.1 Improve selectivity: “sort on the bottom of the sea, not on ship deck”

In all countries, fishers, fisheries managers and scientists admit that the best mitigating strategy is to improve gear selectivity. At the same time, fishers said they cannot do more efforts as they already increased the size of the mesh, and they cannot do more. Mediterranean fishers (Spanish, French, Greek) spoke about the recent improvement with the introduction of the 40 mm square mesh cod-end by trawlers which increased selectivity. For them this rule should be extended to all Mediterranean countries that continue to fish with smaller mesh size. Greek fishers said to be ready to test new gears if they are compensated financially.

French fishers operating in English Channel, Celtic Sea and Bay of Biscay at the beginning of the DiscardLess project didn’t want to test more selective gears. This negative attitude seems to have changed with time, with the realisation of different national projects seeking to improve gear selectivity, on trawlers in particular. These national projects were conducted either by fisheries committees (CarRejet, EODE), by POs (CELSELECT, SURDINE, SURSOLE, ENSURE...) or other organisations (Anglia with REDRESSE) in collaboration with scientists and fishing gear technologists. Trials were conducted to improve fish survival and reduce choke species. Few fishers accepted to participate in these trials. The change of attitude can be attributed to the fear of choke species and the idea that vessels would be inactive for several weeks or months.

The CELSELECT project, carried out by a Bretagne PO in collaboration with scientists, seeks to improve the selectivity of the gear of vessels operating in the Celtic Sea and having problems with choke species (boarfish for which France doesn’t have any quota), horse mackerel and mackerel as by catch. Trials

took place during fishing operations. The device tested is the “T90” mesh in 100 mm in the whole of the terminal part of the trawl. This trial had positive results and that device may probably be adopted by French vessels operating in this area.

The owners of vessels involved in this trial, suggested a modality for calculating the commercial losses on which is based the financial compensation during trials. Two vessels having the same characteristics, targeting the same species, one testing the new device and the other not, should operate side by side in the same area, and then compare their respective catches. This comparison would give a clear idea about the real losses.

Danish fishers also ask for compensation in case of trials; and they also accepted to test the use of camera on board. In France, this was a taboo issue. During the public meeting organised by the DiscardLess project team in France (Paris, November 2018), many participants questioned the team about cameras and the cost of installation. Can this question be interpreted as a change?

In the Azores, fishers are replacing longlines by handlines and discards are lower and there is an increase in fish survival. Longline fishers say they release fish under quota 0 either by taking out the hook when it is possible or by cutting it.

Figures 8 and 9 present the results of national surveys. It is to be noted that fishers are accepting to test new gears if they are compensated. Only 20% of French fishers don't agree. In Greece this percentage reach almost 38% of interviewed fishers.

Figure 8. Adaptation of fishing gears, France

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

Figure 9. Adaptation of fishing gears, Greece

Source: National survey in Greece, 2018, DiscardLess

2.5.2 Change of fishing area and real time closures

When asked how they avoid discards, fishers responded: “We change fishing zone”. Often friends or family members are informed about the presence of small fish.

“We are working in groups (...) and when we are in a “bad area” (a lot of juveniles), we leave as soon as we can. Sometimes, we sail for three or four hours to get away. As soon as we find a good area, we report to the others (...). Nowadays our communication means are very good” (large scale trawler).

In Azores, longliners also turn to other areas in case of undersized fish. But as the deployment of the gear is long, they need more time to react and shift to areas where they are less likely to catch unwanted species. *“My quota of goraz is low, and to avoid this species I am fishing in deeper water (700-1000 meter) where I catch juliana and boca negra”* (Long Line fisher). Moving from one area to another is not perceived as a problem because fishers can return back later during the year or another season. All fishers have the same objective: *“Land fish with high commercial value rather than small ones without value”*. Optimisation of the quota, where quota system is available, is enough to motivate fishers to turn to new areas. For them, *“bringing home small individuals is not our objective”* because, in this way, *“our quotas are quickly consumed”*. Often POs (internal agreement) punished fishers for landing fish having the lower legal size or higher amounts of the allocated daily quota.

So, staying in areas having juveniles or small fish is not profitable for fishers. Thanks to their empirical experiences, fishers avoid areas with nurseries or juveniles.

The idea of real time closures is well understandable and acceptable for fishers. Balearic fishers are ready to implement such rule if needed. In other areas, fishers are more reluctant, although they understand its usefulness. Their reticence is based more on fear of their national administrative system rather than on having to stop fishing in one area. For example, in Greece, trawlers operating in the North Aegean Sea believe that real time closure is a good tool to avoid discards; but given the time needed to validate a decision by the national authorities, they prefer to avoid it. In Greece, real time closures, as all other types of closures, require a national decision, i.e. a Presidential Decree. The whole procedure, administratively, takes approximatively one year to be accomplished and eventually to be published in

the official journal. So fishers will avoid pushing for implementation of real time closures as the current legal framework does not allow such fast decisions.

Fishers are less sceptical about real time closures if it were decided by their organisation or informally within local fishers' groups. But taking management decisions is possible in countries where there are strong fishers' organizations, or POs as in Spain, France, Denmark. In countries where fishers' organisations are weak or inexistent, it is difficult to make them acceptable by all. There is always the possibility that *"others fishers will not respect the rule and will go fishing"* (Greek fisher).

In Azores, real time or seasonal geographical closures are not also welcome. The not acceptability of such closures is the fear to see the area closed permanently. This apprehension is based on their experience because many areas were closed for experimental reasons; but they never reopened. The same fear is found in Greece or in France and for the same reasons: *"if we will inform fisheries authorities that in the area there are small size fish and ask to close it, I am sure the area will close for ever"* (Greek fisher). This negative reaction to permanent closures is justified by the fact that their workspace is nibbled by other users or for biodiversity conservation purposes. Natura 2000 areas, wind or aquaculture farms are already reducing their space. And they don't want to lose more. Mapping zones concentrating juveniles is seen as a good tool to avoid discards; but *"it cannot be done for all species"*. The following figure shows the most favourite solutions for adaptation to the LO. More time to set up a market price, financial compensation to adapt and need for more time are the first solutions mentioned by fishers; increase of quotas and improvement of gear are a little behind. In France, decreasing minimum size of the species doesn't obtain a high score.

Figure 10. Solutions to adapt to the LO: France

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

2.5.3 Choke species

The notion of choke species⁵ is very difficult to be understood by fishers and probably also for persons supervising the fisheries sector. During the first years of the DiscardLess project, none of the interviewed persons mentioned choke species as a potential difficulty that could disturb fishing activities. Over time, this issue became probably the main motivation to discuss the LO, and also to change fishing practices. The first group of people that comprehended this term and its impact on fishing activities were those participating at Advisory Councils meetings, then also other fisheries managers working more locally. Unfortunately, artisanal fishers still do not fully understand the notion and its repercussion on their practices. Choke species is not an exclusive difficulty for fleets operating within the quota system: it affects others too.

For example, France doesn't hold quotas for boarfish, but this species is often caught in the Celtic Sea while vessels target other species present in the area. One fisher said: *"One day, our vessels caught 10 tons of boarfish; and another day we reached 40 tons in the trawl. Our storage place can contain only 25 tons. So what could we do with that fish?"* This quote raises two issues: first, the lack of quota, second, the lack of storage on board. For French fisheries managers and fishers, the question is to ascertain whether they should stay in port during the period of abundance of boarfish.

French fishers don't hold quotas for all species (or insufficient ones). Therefore, they often discard soles, mackerel, herring, Atlantic horse mackerel, etc. In Azores, SSF vessels discard goraz (*Pagellus bogaraveo*) or other species. For countries with enough quotas, the problem of choke species is less crucial because they can exchange quotas between MS. But this is different for countries without a lot of quotas: choke species represent an important issue for them. In all cases, MS should rethink the quota distribution system at national level, and also how they will proceed in quota exchanges.

The CFP regulation provides tools to adjust quotas between MS in a way to reduce the pressure of choke species. One of these tools is the possible exchange of quota: *"(...) in the event of a mismatch between available quotas and actual fishing pattern, Member States should consider adjustments through quota swaps with other Member States, including on a permanent basis. Member States should also consider facilitating the pooling by vessel owners of individual quotas, for example at the level of producer organisations or groups of vessel owners. Ultimately, Member States should consider counting by-catch species against the quota of the target species, depending on the conservation status of the by-catch species.* (29th consideration of EU regulation 1380/2013).

Quota exchanges between Member States have been practiced for many years. They usually take place twice a year, at the beginning of the year and in the last months. Since the introduction of the LO, MS seem to be reluctant about this old practice, mainly because they want to identify the real needs of their own fleets before proceeding to such exchanges. The same attitude is found within POs (French fisheries administration, PO managers).

⁵ A choke species is a term used to describe a species with a low quota that can cause a vessel to stop fishing even if they still have quota for other species.

There are few other possibilities provided by Article 15 to facilitate the issue of choke species, for example the use of a year-to-year flexibility or the interspecies flexibility. Both already applied by MS which are not responding to the needs of LO. Quota uplifting is another tool provided by Article 15 to support LO implementation. This solution doesn't answer the issue of choke species as it is calculated on the percentage of the total. But the lack of data on discards makes it difficult to establish a coherent base for calculation.

2.6 Which use for unwanted catches?

Fishers, administration and environmental NGOs from the Mediterranean Sea, and also French small-scale fishers think that the LO encourages the landing of small fish. And this may contradict the objectives of sustainable development. Because there is always the possibility of targeting undersized fish (now allowed by the LO to be landed) and sell them in a parallel market for human consumption. In some MS, consumers have a preference for small-size fish (hake, red mullet....). Fishers show a preference to use discards for human consumption rather than other uses. For them, small individuals should go for philanthropic purposes. Figure 11 shows that French fishers don't want discards to be used for that end.

Figure 11 Use discards for human consumption, France,

Source: National survey in France 2018, DiscardLess

The use of discards to feed aquaculture fish is contested by almost all fishers. Some of them didn't hesitate to accuse the aquaculture sector of being the main responsible for the LO. The aquaculture lobby is viewed as the main cause for the LO. For fishers, producing fishmeal with wild fish in order to feed aquaculture species is just not acceptable, probably because at the end both products are competing on the market. The fact that landing species that have a high survival rate increases fishers'

doubts concerning the objectives of the LO. For fishers (French, Greek, Spanish, Azores), these species should return back to the sea and would have the chance to grow and be caught later, or feed other wild fish and birds. This is the only acceptable use for these fishers. Dead wild fish contribute already to the ecosystem. So why should they offer it for free to the fishmeal processing industry and to the aquaculture sector?

Figure 12. Use of discards for aquaculture, Greece.

Source: National survey in Greece 2018, DiscardLess

In other areas like Bretagne or Boulogne, fishers say that auctions are not ready to receive discards. None of them has introduced new equipment to maintain fish in good condition. “*There is already no funding for cranes to land fish: who will invest in new infrastructure?*” (fisher in Brittany). In harbours where processing facilities are available, fishers point out that prices offered are very low. The different arguments used by fishers during interviews underline how difficult it will be to use unwanted and unavoidable catch for purposes other than human consumption in MS where this tradition didn’t exist. In small islands, fishers mentioned the absence of processing plants, which makes it difficult to utilize discards.

2.7 Which needs from science and acceptability of observers

During interviews and also during the surveys, fishers and managers were asked about their needs from science and then about the acceptability of observers on board fishing vessels. Few of them said that science can provide them with information and knowledge on how to better adapt to the LO requirements.

The interest of what science can provide is shown also from the participation of stakeholders at the public meetings organised by Discardless in which many fishers and managers participated along the fisheries administration. For example, the FROM Nord, a French PO, was inspired from the work of DiscardLess WP 3 and they are now testing the use of trawl with light.

The following figures show the opinion of fishers responding to the national survey. Figure 13 indicates the views of French fishers, who mainly expressed no clear opinion. Figure 14 shows that Greek fishers are opposed to such support.

Figure 13. Support from Science, France

Figure 14. Support from Science, Greece

Observations on board seem to be more welcome for French fishers (figure 15), with or without compensation. This is not the case for the Greeks (figure 16).

Figure 15. Observers of board, France

Figure 16. Observers on board, Greece

3 Conclusions

This report shows that European fishers have some common ideas concerning the LO and its implementation process. This rule leaves the majority of fishers unsatisfied because it aims at restricting their activities without taking into account the different efforts they have realized in fisheries management. All fishers, small and large-scale, consider that the LOs' main objective is to reduce the operations of trawlers. At the same time, they consider that it is impacting on all of them because all fishing gears produce discards.

The LO will impact negatively fishing activities. This is the other belief that dominates fishers' thinking. A reduction in the profitability of the vessels is considered one of the most important impacts. Increased expenditures and landing of fish with low commercial value can affect the activity of many vessels. For fishers, fishing means bringing to the market fish with high commercial value. For that, they always avoid small individuals or species having low commercial value by changing their zone of operation. Real time closures can be a solution if the administration of Members States manages to act on that promptly, or if fishers can take the decision simply among themselves. Improved fishing gears is a rational objective for fishers. But they doubt whether one can go even further in terms of selectivity.

The issue of choke species is probably the reason that has most contributed to the modification of the attitude of fishers against the LO. Fisheries managers are now asking fishers to register discards to better identify the problems of implementation and provide them with arguments to be used against the LO implementation. Nowadays, fishers and skippers continue to discard and not register discards. But all managers believe that it is time to act and convince them to change behaviour and practices.

Communication and information need good arguments to convince fishers of the importance of the LO. This is not done yet, probably because all national managers don't find the right arguments to explain this rule, considered by all as unjust. But in some harbors PO's managers who used the right arguments have positive results as for example in Boulogne Sur Mer or in Saint Quai Portrieux, fishers started to register discards in logbooks. The Boulogne Sur Mer PO's organised training to show fishers how to feel the logbook. Untill now noone landed discards yet but this is not the case in the Republic of Ireland where one PO convinced fishers to land discards and use them as bait.

The implementation of the LO mainly requires a change of the mentality and that is the most difficult part. Best practices and success stories where a win-win situation is highlighted must be widely presented to the fisheries Community in an effort to achieve their cooperation and actual implementation and on the same time safeguard the provisions of the CFP where fishing activities should contribute to long-term environmental, economic and social sustainability and contribute to increased productivity and to a fair standard of living for the fisheries sector.